

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the third regular issue in 2014. In this issue, 37 authors from 7 countries and 5 continents present in 9 papers a great variety of topics in the subject domains of information systems, software, theory of computation, computer applications and science and technology of learning. My particular thanks go to all reviewers who were involved in the review process of the published articles and also to the members of the editorial board who reviewed articles that did not make it to publication. I'd also like to take this opportunity to gratefully thank all institutions and individuals - including the consortium members, editorial board members and the authors - for all their support and effort to make J.UCS one of the well-recognized journals in computer science.

The authors Renato de Freitas Bulcão-Neto, José Antonio Camacho Guerrero, Paulo Schor, Alessandra Stanquini Lopes, Márcio Branquinho Dutra and Alessandra Alaniz Macedo from Brazil presents their research on the MedLink linking service, which automatically identifies semantic relationships among multilingual clinical cases and makes them available to users as hyperlinks.

The authors Antonina Danylenko, Jonas Lundberg and Welf Löwe from Sweden unify in their paper different classification approaches by introducing a Decision Algebra which defines models for classification as higher order decision functions abstracting from their implementations using decision trees, decision rules, or decision tables.

Naglaa Fathy, Tarek F. Gharib, Nagwa Badr, Abdulfattah S. Mashat and Ajith Abraham focus in a collaborative research between Egypt, Saudi Arabia and the USA on a personalized approach for re-ranking search results using user preferences.

Gustavo Rodrigues Galvão and Zanoni Dias from Brazil address in their work the problem of sorting by transpositions and introducing 3 alternative approaches for approximating the transposition distance.

In the international collaboration of researchers from Malaysia and Austria, Narayanan Kulathuramaiyer, Hermann Maurer and Rizwan Mehmood investigate aspects of the reliability of information on the web.

Luis Llana, Enrique Martín-Martín, Cristóbal Pareja-Flores and J. Ángel Velázquez-Iturbide from Spain present in their article FLOP, a user-friendly system for automated program assessment reduce the number of management tasks.

A Middleware architecture for dynamic adaptation in ubiquitous computing is presented in the work of João Lopes, Rodrigo Souza, Cláudio Geyer, Cristiano Costa, Jorge Barbosa, Ana Pernas and Adenauer Yamin from Brazil.

Nuria Losada, María J. Martin, Gabriel Rodríguez and Patricia González from Spain present in their paper an extension to CPPC (ComPiler for Portable Checkpointing) to provide fault tolerance support to OpenMP applications.

Finally, José Antonio Mateo, María del Carmen Ruiz, Hermenegilda Maciá and Juan José Pardo from Spain cover in their paper a formal study of routing protocols for wireless sensor networks.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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